

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.7: 2nd Dissemination Plan

WP7 – Dissemination

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D 7.7 – 2 nd Dissemination Plan			
Work Package	WP 7 - Dissemination			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	01 June 2016	Actual	03 June 2016
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	PLAN02			
Responsible Author	Mr. Vassileios Tsekeridis			
Contributions from	Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis, Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou, Ms. Maria Vogiatzi, Dr. Reinhard Busch			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.1	26/2/2016	Draft	Document structure	Mr. Vassileios Tsekeridis
1.0	5/5/2016	First version	Overview of the deliverable's progress	Mr. Christodoulos Keratidis, Ms. Panagiota Syropoulou, Ms. Maria Vogiatzi
2.0	1/6/2016	Final	Final Amended after internal review procedure	Dr. Reinhard Busch

Disclaimer

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© STEP Consortium, 2015

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	5
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Overview	5
2.2	Objectives	5
2.3	Expected Results	6
3	Dissemination plan from June 2016 until the end of the project	6
3.1	Dissemination tools.....	6
3.1.1	STEP visual identity	7
3.1.2	STEP website	7
3.1.3	Social Media.....	7
3.1.4	STEP promotional material	9
3.1.4.1	Videos	9
3.1.4.2	Newsletters	9
3.1.4.3	Press releases.....	10
3.1.4.4	Leaflets and posters	10
3.1.4.5	Other printed material	10
3.2	Dissemination activities	11
3.2.1	Network of Interest.....	11
3.2.2	Mass media communication	12
3.2.3	Press releases.....	12
3.2.4	Publications.....	12
3.2.5	Posts in non-project channels.....	13
3.2.6	Participation in targeted events.....	13
3.2.7	Organisation of project events.....	14
3.2.7.1	Launch events	14
3.2.7.2	Open events.....	14
3.2.7.3	Webinars.....	15
3.2.8	Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives.....	15
4	Future dissemination in the pilot countries	16
4.1	Local Dissemination Strategy Outline	16
4.2	Action Plan - Monitoring	17
5	Monitoring, Reporting & Evaluation	23
6	Dissemination timeplan	24
7	Conclusions	26

ANNEX I – Reporting Templates.....	27
Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications.....	27
Template for Reporting Dissemination Events.....	27
ANNEX II – Report on the formation of the local core teams	29

Table of Figures

Figure 1. EU emblem.....	7
Figure 2: The Greek STEP Facebook page	8
Figure 3: STEP post-its design	11

1 Executive summary

This deliverable concerns the Second Dissemination Plan of STEP. The current document is an updated version of the 1st Dissemination Plan delivered on the August 2015. It offers details on the dissemination activities to be executed from June 2016 until the end of the project and provides the pilot partners with detailed specifications on how to disseminate the project to targeted groups in their area.

This updated dissemination plan describes the project's dissemination objectives and measures for achieving them throughout the duration of the project (Chapter 2). In Chapter 3, a general overview of the STEP dissemination plan from June 2016 until the end of the project, together with instructions and recommendations on how to prepare the dissemination tools and activities, is presented. The Local Dissemination Strategies for the pilot areas are described in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 describes the procedure of the STEP dissemination monitoring and reporting, while in Chapter 6 the timeplan for the preparation and deliverable of the most important dissemination tools and activities for the next period is presented.

2 Introduction

2.1 Overview

This document represents an updated version of the first STEP Dissemination Plan and, additionally, intends to address some relevant issues raised during the first year of the project's operation, such as:

- The need to revise the dissemination plan so that the used tools and the performed activities better fulfil the requirements of the STEP target audience.
- The need to create and disseminate knowledge relevant to the STEP objectives, and create discussions and synergies in the specific area.
- The fact that the purpose and effectiveness of the envisaged dissemination actions should be measured by appropriate Key Performance Indicators.
- The need of the pilot partners to receive specific instructions on how to disseminate the project, which has emerged during the 1st year of the project.

2.2 Objectives

The objectives of the STEP dissemination Work Package (WP7) are to:

- Raise awareness of the youth community on the project. Achieve diversity and inclusiveness by involving a demographically balanced group of young people reflecting the community and the community needs.
- Raise awareness of local, regional and national policy makers and public bodies, especially in the field of environment.
- Maximise participation in operations offered by the developed platform/ mobile app through the project by drawing attention of young people.

- Ensure efficient communication and understanding regarding the project, obtain support and encourage participation of all stakeholders involved, as well as the wide public in disseminating information and exploiting results.
- Introduce new patterns of conduct in the target groups - the end users of the project's main outputs and results.
- Integrate targeted approaches, eliciting enhanced networking to disseminate new and sustainable ideas, with the use of innovative and creative means.
- Establish formal and non- formal networks, also strengthening and valorizing existing ones, for the exchanging of ideas and practices, in order to develop the sense of a community in participating in decision making in the fields of environment and sustainable development and the public sphere in general.

Thus, the dissemination strategy aims to engage all stakeholders involved in environmental policy in a positive interaction, harnessing global experience from experts and local experience from participatory events.

2.3 *Expected Results*

The expected results of the STEP dissemination strategy are:

- Awareness raising about the project activities, informing the target audiences and the general public about the STEP project. This will be done mainly during the initial stage of the project and actively supported by the dissemination tools. However, during the whole lifetime of STEP, the consortium will create publicity of the project to attract potential future stakeholders and ensure maximum impact.
- Communication to the target groups of the benefits that the project provides and of ways to exploit the results.
- Promotion of active participation in the project, e.g. via the attendance in the project workshops enhancing the links to other projects and stimulating the participation in the STEP External Expert Advisory Board. This will be done to promote the take up of the STEP platform by an increasing number of local authorities and young people.

3 *Dissemination plan from June 2016 until the end of the project*

3.1 *Dissemination tools*

In this Chapter, a general overview of the STEP dissemination tools that are planned to be prepared and the dissemination activities that will be performed from June 2016 until the end of the project are presented. In addition, instructions and recommendations on how to prepare these tools and activities are provided, so that it is ensured that all partners disseminate the project information on the most effective and appropriate way. In addition, these instructions ensure that:

- All partners have access to the same information at the same time
- All partners are aware of the development status of the STEP platform
- The project's information is equally fast transmitted to all partners
- Appropriate formats and effective communication procedures are used
- The transmitted information minimises overload, is fast accessible and reduced to the essential.

3.1.1 *STEP visual identity*

The STEP visual identity has already been established from the early beginning of the project (M3). All project partners should use the agreed colour palette and logos for any graphics or colour design of STEP throughout the duration of the project and after its completion. Moreover, the STEP QR code, the STEP banners, and the prepared dissemination templates should be used appropriately without any modification. In addition, partners should not forget to include the EU emblem and a clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme in any dissemination material they prepare. Finally, "any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency or European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains".

Figure 1. EU emblem

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493.

3.1.2 *STEP website*

A user-friendly, well-designed and easily accessible website has been established and is functioning in its full capacity. The STEP website is available at www.step4youth.eu. Within the duration of the project, the website will be constantly updated and its content will be subject to modification based on the project evolving needs. Especially when the STEP platform is developed and the pilot operations begin, the project website will be significantly revised so as to offer better visibility on the pilots' results.

The website activity is and will be monitored using the Google Analytics, a tool that tracks and reports visitor traffic and gives a complete picture of the behaviour of the website audience.

3.1.3 *Social Media*

Dedicated social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Google+ and YouTube) were created early in the project (Month 5). These accounts will be sustained and continuously fed with new elements as they represent an important way for the consortium to be in touch with the STEP target groups, and especially young people. PLANO2 is the overall responsible for managing and feeding these accounts. However, all project partners are encouraged to upload posts and send to PLANO2 any interesting information that can be communicated via the STEP social media accounts.

In addition to these general social media accounts, which will contain general information relevant to the project’s progress, environmental news and international news about the participation of young people in decision making, the project pilot partners will create local social media accounts for the STEP pilot implementation in their area. Each pilot partner is free to decide which social media better meets the needs of the local community and create an account until September 2016 (Month 16) in their language. This account will present the progress and the results of the pilot implementation of the STEP project in each specific area and will be managed by the corresponding pilot partner. Partner ROC has created a Facebook page in [Greek](#) where they either share the posts uploaded in the general STEP Facebook account or upload new posts targeted to residents of Crete. The other pilot partners had also expressed their intention to create a page in their language so that they boost the dissemination of the project’s results but also to attract more young people to participate in the STEP pilot implementation in their area. In order to maximise the audience to which the STEP results will be communicated, each pilot partner will run social media campaigns with advertisements and various motives (contests, prizes, etc.).

Figure 2: The Greek STEP Facebook page

3.1.4 *STEP promotional material*

3.1.4.1 *Videos*

A short promotional video has been created for the STEP project in order to maximise its visibility and explain the objectives of the project in a stimulating way. The video was produced by a professional video production team, and includes sound effects, voice over and music. The STEP partners, and especially PLANO2 and DRAXIS, were in constant collaboration with the video production team to ensure that the final video would be of high quality and it would clearly explain the project's objectives.

This first promotional video is available in the STEP YouTube channel and can be directly accessed via the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R90AgFkdnJc> or by searching "STEP Click your environment now".

All project partners are motivated to promote the STEP video in any relevant means and events in which they participate throughout the duration of the project. In addition, the STEP pilot partners are required to translate the content of the video in their language and add subtitles, always in collaboration with PLANO2. These translated videos will be used for the better visibility of the STEP pilot implementation in each pilot area with the aim to speak in the language of youth and effectively motivate the young local population to participate in the local project activities.

In addition, an online tutorial, for users of the STEP platform (public authorities, young people and NGOs) showing how the STEP platform works will be prepared and made available on the website (November 2016). It will also be uploaded to social media for additional exposure.

3.1.4.2 *Newsletters*

Short, regular newsletters are a key dissemination tool to inform relevant target audiences about the progress of the STEP project. Thus, they will be produced and circulated appropriately every six months and they will consist of brief articles and updates about the project progress.

The first issue of the STEP newsletters was produced and disseminated in November 2015 (M6), while the second issue is under preparation and it is expected to be circulated in June 2016 (M13). The content of the following issues will include information on the project progress (platform development, project meetings, results of the pilot implementations), as well as updates on the project events and the third-party events in which the project was presented or is planned to be presented in the future. PLANO2 is the overall responsible for the preparation of the STEP newsletters, while all project partners will be asked to provide their contribution and approve the content of each issue.

In order to engage as many stakeholders as possible, the STEP partners are encouraged to distribute the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project. Apart from this, interested parties can subscribe to the STEP newsletters on the project's website. Each issue will be disseminated to the STEP email list, published on the website and announce through social media channels for further dissemination. All STEP newsletters will be also sent to the project Network of Interest through Mailchimp, and to the project External Expert Advisory Board via email.

3.1.4.3 *Press releases*

Press releases about the project activities and results will be prepared in English and distributed through various media channels throughout the duration of the project. It is planned that a new press release will be prepared whenever an important project milestone is achieved or a significant result is emerged. PLANO2 is the overall responsible for the preparation of the press releases and their distribution to international channels. ePress releases with dissemination to online media and bloggers, and dissemination of press information to digital opinion leaders publishing in unofficial media channels will also be explored to create additional outreach. Additionally, each project partner is responsible to translate the press releases in their language, identify the relevant local media and distribute the STEP press releases to them.

So far, two press releases have already been distributed: one for the announcement of the project acceptance, and one about the results of the STEP kick-off meeting. The next edition is expected to be released when the STEP pilot operations are about to start (November 2016).

3.1.4.4 *Leaflets and posters*

A first version of the STEP leaflet has been prepared early in the project (M6). The leaflet was prepared in English by PLANO2 with the agreement of all partners on its content. The STEP pilot partners have translated the leaflet in their language (Italian, Spanish, Catalan, Greek, Turkish) and distributed it to the pilot sites in order to maximise engagement. Furthermore, partner LINGUATEC translated the leaflet into German so that it could be distributed at the "[Global Event for Digital Business- CeBit 2016](#)" and other forthcoming events in Germany.

However, from the feedback received from the pilot partners and the audience reached, the need to prepare a second project leaflet that better meets the consortium needs emerged. This leaflet will be a smaller one in a double sided A5 paper. It will also be printed in recycled paper so that the environmental aspect of the project is emphasised. The leaflet will be prepared by PLANO2 in collaboration with the pilot partners and YEE until the end of June 2016 (M13), it will be printed by each partner who wants to use it, and it will be distributed by any relevant dissemination channels until the end of the project and after its completion.

The STEP poster was prepared in English and the language of the pilot partners in M6, was published in the STEP website, and has been used in project meeting, workshops, conferences and other events in which the STEP consortium has participated so far. According to the needs and expectations from each dissemination event, the content of the poster will be updated throughout the duration of the project. PLANO2 is responsible for these updates in collaboration with all partners.

3.1.4.5 *Other printed material*

As recommended by the pilot partner partners, further targeted promotional material should be prepared to ensure the maximum dissemination of the project, especially to young people. Indicative material that was proposed is: business cards, post-its, USB sticks, cloth bags, hats, etc. Each pilot partner is responsible to prepare the design, print and distribute the dissemination material that better meets their own needs, always under the supervision of PLANO2. Any printed dissemination material will be aligned with the relevant guidelines of the European Commission, will agree with the graphical identity of the project, and clearly state the EC's support.

So far, STEP business cards, post-its, USB sticks, cloth bags, and hats have been prepared and are about to be appropriately distributed throughout the duration of the project by all project partners.

Figure 3: STEP post-its design

3.2 Dissemination activities

3.2.1 Network of Interest

The aim of the establishment of a Network of Interest is to act as a main dissemination pole for the engagement of the STEP target groups. An initial contact list of the members of the STEP Network of Interest has been established, while the methodology of recruitment and the relevant activities carried out so far are described in D7.4-1st Network of Interest (M12). Until now, the Network of Interest contact list contains 887 individual entries (with a target number of 1.000 entries until the end of the project). The establishment and management of a Network of Interest will be an ongoing activity during the entire life of the project, as well as after the end of the project. Throughout the duration of the project, any additional relevant contacts of the project partners will be added to the STEP Network of Interest. Furthermore, the STEP “brand” recognition and the dissemination activities will enlarge our network of contacts, and these will be added to the Network of Interest.

The main objective of future engagement with the STEP Network of Interest is to maintain communication with the existing and future members of the network, to keep up their interest and continue the interaction with them. Until now member engagement has taken place through a professional mass emailing solution (Mailchimp). New tools and actions to maintain participation and encourage active participation and expansion of the network will be employed in the period to come. Such actions and methods include:

- A semi-annual newsletter that will be sent to all members of the network in order to keep them informed of general news and progress of STEP project.
- Posts to the STEP social media accounts by inviting the members of the network to “Like” and “Follow” the accounts.
- Webinars: A series of webinars will be executed after the first release of the STEP eParticipation platform. This process will give the opportunity to the members of the network to provide a public feedback and get familiar with the platform functionalities.

Further recommendations for the network development include: a) Actions should be taken to increase the members of the Core Group; b) Increase and diversify the members from different countries; c) Expansion of entries from countries outside EU with a focus on Turkey; and d) Increase the members from other types of organisations, especially from public authorities.

3.2.2 Mass media communication

The scope of the mass media communication activities will be to inform the general public about the STEP project through news agencies and mass media with general or specialised interests. These media include national and international TV and radio channels, web media, newspapers and magazines with a wide audience, such as the official web portal of the European Commission (<http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm>) and EurActiv (<http://www.euractiv.com/>).

The mass media communication will be initiated when the STEP platform is ready and the pilot operation begins (December 2016), so that tangible results are presented to the general public. In order to avoid discrepancies among the information that will be communicated in mass media from the project partners, PLANO2 is going to prepare an indicative interview template. The STEP partners are encouraged to disseminate the STEP project through mass media on a regular basis. However, the official contact with the mass media will be made by the WP7 leader through the official email account of the STEP project.

3.2.3 Press releases

Press releases will be issued whenever important project milestones are achieved. They will include important information such as the objective of the project, milestones reached and results achieved so far, and partners involved. The partners will prepare press releases targeting the local or national press throughout the duration of the project describing the objectives of the project in a simple, jargon free language, while they will highlight the benefits for a specific region/ country if needed.

The project press releases will be launched by PLANO2 which will inform DRAXIS prior to any release, while any partner that wants to launch a press release is encouraged to contact PLANO2 first. All press releases will be archived and will be available to the public through the project website.

3.2.4 Publications

It is expected that the STEP project will result in at least 2 scientific papers published in peer-reviewed journals until the end of the project. Project partners are encouraged to collaborate with each other and jointly prepare articles relevant to the STEP project. A draft of any project-related scientific paper that is

about to be sent to a journal will be shared with all partners at least 7 days before publication, while the final version will be sent only under the permission of the project coordinator.

For scientific publications related to STEP, beneficiaries must ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user). The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

3.2.5 Posts in non-project channels

As for all the dissemination activities of the project, uploading posts to non-project channels is an ongoing activity that will continue to be executed throughout the whole duration of the project. These channels include blogs, LinkedIn and Facebook groups, and EU websites relevant to e-participation, e-governance, environmental policy making, sustainability, and youth participation. Uploading posts to such channels aims to boost the visibility of project news and results so that the maximum target audience is reached.

3.2.6 Participation in targeted events

Networking is a crucial way to share and exchange professional experiences and disseminate the project results. A common way to achieve an effective dissemination is the participation of the STEP partners in targeted events where STEP will be presented. Personal contacts and presentations through attendance at relevant workshops, trade shows and other events are ranking top of the list of most popular dissemination channels. All project partners are encouraged to identify relevant local/ national/ international events in which the STEP project can be presented and reach a wide audience, and report these to PLANO2. After the agreement of DRAXIS, the project partners can participate in any event they wish under the instructions of PLANO2 on how to communicate the project objectives and results. After the participation in any event, the participated partner should send a full report to PLANO2 describing the scope of the event, the means of the project dissemination, and the volume of audience reached. These reports should be prepared in the template provided by PLANO2 at the beginning of the project and is available in ANNEX I – Reporting Templates.

Some of the relevant forthcoming events in which the STEP project will be presented are summarised in the following template.

Table 1: Targeted forthcoming third-party events

Event	Location	Date	Link	Participant
16th European Conference on e-Government	Ljubljana, Slovenia	16 - 17 /6/2016	http://www.academic-conferences.org/conferences/eceg/	DRAXIS
Contemporary Political Youth Culture and Communication Symposium	UK	18-19/7/2016	http://goo.gl/KH3sfj	ABERTAY

IFIP e-participation conference	Portugal	5-8/9/2016	http://goo.gl/AXhehy	ABERTAY
INSCI 2016-3rd International conference on Internet Science	Florence, Italy	12-14/9/2016	http://internetscienceconference.eu/	CERTH, DRAXIS
5 th International Conference on Industrial and Hazardous Waste Management	Crete, Greece	27-30/9/2016	http://goo.gl/AXhehy	ROC
7 th Forum of Urban Intelligence and Sustainability	Malaga, Spain	5-6/10/2016	http://greencities.malaga.eu/	MDV

3.2.7 Organisation of project events

All project partners are motivated to organise local targeted events in order to disseminate the STEP project in their area and motivate local communities to actively participate in the project. The scope of these events is to increase youth awareness on the STEP platform and engage further external stakeholders, such as public organisations, NGOs, strategic decision makers, policy makers, think tanks, scholars, public and private administrations, etc. Each partner can evaluate what kind of event better meets the needs of the local people and can be an effective means of dissemination. The events will be organised under the instructions of the WP7 leader and after the agreement of the project coordinator.

3.2.7.1 Launch events

When the STEP platform is ready, each pilot partner will organise and hold a launch event in their area. These launch events will be set up in order to introduce the STEP platform to the general public and allow the testing of the STEP concept in a wide range of target groups. In addition, in the launch events dedicated workshops will take place for those who are not familiar with the use of digital tools, aiming to ensure that the STEP procedures will not result in discriminatory practices or unfair treatment. In the same framework, info kiosks will be placed outside the event venue for those with no internet access and special dissemination material will be designed and distributed.

The responsible pilot partner will try to build liaisons with the mass media. Representatives of the most popular local media (TV channels, radio, newspapers, and magazines) and organisations (e.g. local environmental NGOs) will be invited to take part in the events and act as the main dissemination pole for the project in the local community. Both prior and after the event, the responsible pilot partner should send a relevant press release to the local media. After the completion of the event, the same partner should in detail report on the result of the launch event to PLANO2 using the reporting template prepared.

3.2.7.2 Open events

Open events will be organised to present STEP to any interested stakeholder and the general public. Representatives of local NGOs and public authorities with in-depth knowledge in decision making procedures for youth and environment will be invited in these events so that they bring their own knowledge and

experience on relevant topics, and give their feedback and suggestions. These events can be categorised in two groups:

- **Project Workshops.** Two workshops will be set up in order to provide an overview of the project objectives and activities, present and discuss the results of the project, share experiences and lessons learned to stakeholders and scientific community. The events will include talks and presentations from the STEP partners, but also from invited speakers that have studied related topics to the STEP project, such as representatives of relevant activities. The workshops will be organised close to the end of the project, so that results from the STEP pilot operations can be presented and discussed. The venues of the workshops will be strategically selected so that maximum audience will be achieved and they will be agreed by all STEP partners.
- **Conference.** A big conference or a TEDx-like event will be organised at the end of the project in order to present the results achieved and the lessons learnt to the general public. The venue of the conference will be agreed among all partners.

3.2.7.3 *Webinars*

PLANO2 and DRAXIS will organise webinars with the aim of reaching key people who may be interested to use and exploit the STEP platform. In these webinars, the members of the STEP Network of Interest will be invited to participate so that they can act as a dissemination pole for the engagement of the STEP target groups.

The aim of the webinars is to inform and familiarise the users with the STEP project and the platform. The webinars will be organised through an online conferencing tool and will have a short duration (30 – 40 minutes), while the potential participants will receive emails about the webinars' date and access instructions.

Reports of the results and attendance in the webinars will be prepared by PLANO2 and disseminated to all project partners.

3.2.8 *Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives*

In an ecosystem full of emerging initiatives on citizens' and, especially, youth's participation in decision making, STEP will continuously approach existing stakeholders, networks and initiatives in a collaborative manner. In doing so, STEP can benefit from other organisations' lessons learned, feedback and ideas by building a better product and increasing its viability over time.

The STEP consortium has been in contact with several relevant activities and exchanged information with them. Moreover, we share visibility by uploading information of each other's projects to websites and social media accounts, while physical meetings will be planned when the STEP pilot operation begins. The most relevant ones will also be invited to participate in the STEP events and share their experience with our target audience.

4 Future dissemination in the pilot countries

4.1 Local Dissemination Strategy Outline

Within the context of the general Dissemination Strategy of the project, a specialised Dissemination Strategy outline has been developed, in order to provide guidelines for the planning and implementation of each one of the Local Dissemination Strategies in the pilot areas. In the 1st Dissemination Plan, the local dissemination strategy has been structured in four phases, in order to make use of a variety of activities and tools. Upon consultation with the local partners and taking into account the progress of the project, the content of each one of the dissemination strategy phases has been further specified as follows:

1st Phase: Commitment of the Core Team

During the first phase, the project partners who are responsible for the implementation of the local dissemination strategy should form a core team which will coordinate the dissemination strategy and the engagement of the local stakeholders. The core team will comprise members of each partners' project team as well as experts from related fields with high-level of knowledge and experience in policy making and environmental issues. The core team members should have a clear view on the scope and objectives of the project and specifically the STEP eParticipation platform. In this direction, a main task of the core team would be to effectively communicate and disseminate the potential benefits from the uptake of the platform in their specific field of expertise, raising awareness and engaging the relevant stakeholders.

2nd Phase: Knowledge exchange

During the second phase the project, the core team will provide the necessary knowledge dissemination towards the most interested and active parties on local level. Local thematic workshops will be organised to communicate the project's objectives and outputs in relation to the local needs and priorities. The target groups will be local stakeholders (local NGOs and youth & environmental organisations, active communities, etc.) as well as local authorities and business bodies and other stakeholders concerned on local level (journalists, local media, etc.). The objective will be to build synergies and co-organise participatory events targeted to young people in the next phase.

3rd Phase: Action motivation

During the third phase a set of local participatory events will be organised. The activities will be especially targeted to enhance participation from young people from local level, disseminating the projects objectives towards them, while providing them with the appropriate tools and motivate them to participate actively in the activities of the project, mainly the STEP eParticipation platform, in order to communicate their own message to the parties concerned (local authorities, policy making bodies, etc.). At the same time, the results of the participatory events will provide useful experience data for experts in order to expand and assess the current knowledge and disseminate the project's outcomes.

4th Phase: Feedback and Dissemination

The fourth phase includes all dissemination streams that will result from the experience gained by the first three phases. All the above concerned parties (project partners, field experts, local stakeholders, young participants, etc.) will make use and exploit the experience from the dissemination activities (information events, participatory events), as means of communicating themselves and creating a positive pressure stream towards the stakeholders concerned with policy making and environmental policy, on local and

global level. The relevant means to be used include publications and mass media entries, newsletters and information and publicity activities (e.g. participation in events, public presentations, etc.).

In the next section a detailed action plan for each of the 4 phases is provided, specifying the objectives and content of each phase, as well as the responsibilities for the local partners and the monitoring measures to be used.

4.2 Action Plan - Monitoring

Action Plan 1st phase: Months 14-16 (July 2016 – September 2016)

The following months of the project are crucial for building local capacities, through the engagement of local experts and facilitators from various domains, with relevance to the objectives of the dissemination strategy on each area. A core team of at least 5 persons from each pilot will be formed comprised by both members of the pilot partner and relevant external experts. The responsibility of the members of the pilot partners will be to monitor and implement the local dissemination strategy, while the responsibility of the external experts will be to act as local ambassadors for the further dissemination of STEP in the particular area. In order to inform the relevant experts and ensure their commitment to the core team, the partners may contact them individually (e.g. personal communication over phone, e-mail, etc.) or launch targeted calls for relevant experts.

Moreover, during the same period targeted public events (conferences, press conferences, etc.) will be organised in order to ensure wider information on the project and the upcoming activities.

Specifically, following the planning of the communication activities for phase 1 of the local dissemination strategy, the relevant tasks for each partner during Months 14-16 are presented in the following table:

Indicative timeline: Months 14 to 16	
Comune Di Sant' Agata del Bianco:	
Core team	Potential members of the core team include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● partner's project team; ● Civitas Solis Association.
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); ● local mass media & social media ● peer groups. <p><u>Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● public events & press conferences; ● posters & flyers; ● information points.
Mollet de Valles Municipality	
Core team	Potential members of the core team include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● partner's project team (civil servants & councillors); ● Esplai Xivarri; ● Club Muntanyenc;

D7.7: 2nd Dissemination Plan

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Agroecological Association of Gallecs; 🔴 Geoblau (private company specialized in environment and sustainability) 🔴 Consortium of Gallecs; 🔴 LA Era: center for young people ; 🔴 Secondary Schools of the city; 🔴 Participation Census of the City; 🔴 Morats I Torrats (cultural Associations); 🔴 Council of the City (participatory body);
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); 🔴 Local newspapers 🔴 Local TV 🔴 Local radio 🔴 Advertisements in sport facilities 🔴 Secondary schools (mailing, access to classroom) 🔴 local mass media & social media and youth-related websites; Facebook, Twitter <p><u>Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 public events & press conferences; 🔴 posters & flyers; 🔴 STEP “business cards”; 🔴 information points.
Valdemoro Municipality	
Core team	<p>Potential members of the core team include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 partner’s project team; 🔴 experts from the targeted stakeholders
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); 🔴 youth associations’ forum; 🔴 Centre for Youth Information and Documentation; 🔴 local mass media (TV & radio, thematic publications/issues); <p><u>Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 School & high school activities; 🔴 Festivities activities; 🔴 Youth activities 🔴 Other activities (conferences, meetings, etc.).
Region of Crete	
Core team	<p>Potential members of the core team include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 partner’s project team; 🔴 experts from the targeted areas (see below).
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); 🔴 social media – Greek Facebook & Twitter account;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • youth-related websites; • local mass media (TV & radio, newspapers); <p><u>Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • public events on all 4 Regional Units (Chania, Heraklion, Rethymno & Lasithi) • posters & leaflets; • USB sticks and post-its.
Hatay Metropolitan Municipality	
Core team	<p>Potential members of the core team include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • partner’s project team; • expert group on environment; • academics; • Hatay Smart Eco-City Agency.
Communication channels & measures	<p><u>Channels:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • local authorities websites (municipality & local associations); • social media and youth-related websites; • local mass media (TV & radio, newspapers); <p><u>Measures:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • conferences – eco-city environment festivals; • surveys; • informational material (Leaflets, posters, hats with STEP Logo, STEP Videos).

Monitoring & evaluation – Phase 1:

Each partner should report on the WP7 leader on the undertaken activities for the formation of the core team. For this, the following measures will be taken:

Activities	Monitoring	Deadline
Information activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on information activities (events, websites, mass media, etc.) 	Month 16 (September 2016)
Formation of a core team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of core team members • Agreements of commitment (role, expertise & tasks) 	Month 16 (September 2016)

Action Plan 2nd phase: Months 17-19 (October 2016 – December 2016)

The objective of the 2nd phase of the dissemination strategy is to engage local stakeholders in discussion and interaction, in order to coordinate the organisation of participatory activities for the introduction of young people to the STEP platform. The interaction will be facilitated through local workshops which will take place on each area, by the members of the core team, while the participants will include local stakeholders, representatives of local authorities, public policy bodies and local organisations, etc.

The programme of the workshops will include:

D7.7: 2nd Dissemination Plan

- a brief presentation of the STEP project (objectives, outputs, results, etc.) and platform;
- brief presentation of the scope and objectives of the relevant local pilot activities;
- each of the presentation of the pilot activities will be followed by a thematic discussion among the participants, aiming to identify ways to enhance youth participation more effectively;
- the core teams' experts will facilitate discussions and guide the formation of a draft agenda for the organisation of participatory activities to enhance youth participation;
- 2-3 participatory activities (using the tools provided in the 1st Dissemination Plan) should be drafted, which are to be organised in the occasion of local events/ festivals within the following 12 months;

The participants of the workshops will cooperate with the core team in the organisation of the respective activities in the months following the workshops.

Specification on the target groups and thematic areas, as identified in the planning stage of the dissemination strategy, is provided in the following table:

Indicative timeline: Months 17 to 19	
Comune Di Sant' Agata del Bianco:	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cultural and social associations; • secondary schools; • youth organisations – youth councils; • environmental organisations; • local municipalities – association of municipalities of the Locride area.
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • re-use, recycling and reduce of waste; • water management; • green spaces.
Mollet de Valles Municipality	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural and sport associations; • Secondary schools; • Civic, cultural and sport public centres; • Consortium of Gallecs; • Regional authorities & associations.
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Action Plan for Young People (topics related to environment and sustainability); • Municipal Action Plan (topics related to environment and sustainability); • Food Policy at local level (ecological and environmentally friendly food, short circuits of distribution, etc); • Urban and social gardens; • Environmental volunteering; • Nature itineraries (leisure and environmental education); • air pollution; • green spaces – urban re-naturing/ revitalisation of urban spaces; • sustainable use of environmental resources; • management of protected areas; • recycling ; • energy efficiency.
Valdemoro Municipality	
Target groups - Key	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental NGOs. (Espartal-Ecologistas en Acción, Animal protection, Aiba Association, etc.)

D7.7: 2nd Dissemination Plan

stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Schools and High Schools/ Education centres; 🔴 youth associations and youth groups; 🔴 sports clubs.
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 creation of green spaces; 🔴 efficient use of environmental resources 🔴 sustainable management of protected areas (Parque Regional del Sureste); 🔴 green transportation (e.g. bicycles).
Region of Crete	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 “Ecocrete” network (umbrella organisation) (www.ecocrete.gr) 🔴 Local sports clubs; 🔴 Local cultural organisations; 🔴 Informal groups (scouts, university students clubs, etc.).
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 management of Natura 2000 areas; 🔴 waste disposal; 🔴 energy efficiency, climate change, environmental risks and causes for natural disasters; 🔴 marine spatial planning & integrated coastal zone management.
Hatay Metropolitan Municipality	
Target groups - Key stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Environmental NGO’s & Companies; 🔴 Chamber of Commerce; 🔴 Farmers’ association; 🔴 local municipalities (environment heads); 🔴 forest related business 🔴 hospitals & public agencies.
Targeted areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 biodiversity (esp. medicine & aromatic plants); 🔴 urban ecology; 🔴 water management; 🔴 climate change.

Monitoring & evaluation – Phase 2:

Each partner should report on the WP7 leader on the undertaken activities for the engagement of stakeholders and the thematic workshops. For this, the following measures will be taken **until month 19** of the project:

Activities	Monitoring	Deadline
Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Local workshop proceedings (agenda, participants’ list & proceedings report) 	Month 19 (December, 2016)
Participatory activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔴 Draft proposals for participatory activities discussed, including the relevant local stakeholders involved and targeted thematic area 	Month 19 (December, 2016)

Action Plan 3rd phase: Months 20-30 (January 2017 – November 2017)

During the third phase the main targeted audience of young people is to be approached, with the aim to engage them to a series of participatory open events (such as fair hunts, festivals, interactive simulation events, etc.). The local partners in cooperation with local stakeholders will organise 2-3 participatory

activities on local and/ or regional level, within the occasion of local popular festivities and events. The draft proposals for the participatory activities prepared in the local workshops (phase 2) will be further elaborated and should be submitted to the WP7 leader **by month 24**.

To this end, the partners should ensure to:

- Develop an elaborated proposal for the participatory activities;
- Monitor the coordination of the local stakeholders;
- Ensure the relevant resources for the effective communication and promotion of the activities (organise mass media & social media campaigns, distribute informational material, etc.);
- Support the organisation of the activities within their area of jurisdiction (e.g. provide municipal space for infopoints, etc.)

The final context and specific activities of the events will be decided upon consensus among the local stakeholders in cooperation with the WP7 leader, **until month 25**. Also, necessary for the effectiveness of the activities of the 3rd phase is that the STEP platform has been put into pilot operation, in order to engage pilot users and enhance participation in the platform. The partners will provide adequate information and guidance on using the STEP platform and applications.

Finally, the activities should be organised **until month 28**, leaving adequate time-frame for the gathering and presentation of the results.

Monitoring & evaluation – Phase 3:

Each partner should report on the WP7 leader on the undertaken activities. For this, the following measures will be taken **until month 28** of the project:

Activities	Monitoring	Deadline
Organisation of participatory activities	• Full proposals for participatory activities	Month 24 (May, 2017)
	• Final concept and action plan for participatory activities	Month 25 (June, 2017)
	• Report on the organisation of participatory activities	Month 28 (September, 2017)

Action plan 4th Phase: Months 10-30 (March 2016 – November 2017)

The fourth phase includes a set of parallel dissemination activities, targeted on local level, which will provide dissemination for the main project context, objectives, activities and outputs, as well as information and publicity regarding the organisation of local activities (1st, 2nd & 3rd Phase).

Specifically, each partner will be responsible for the following tasks:

- **Project website – Social Media:** Provide information on regular basis to the WP7 leader for the update of the project website and create local social media pages/accounts, available in local language.
- **Press Releases:** Update and integrate the list with local press and mass media and provide performance data to the WP7 leader for the editing of press releases. Also, targeted coverage (interviews, messages, etc.) will be scheduled on local mass media (TV, radio, internet media) within the occasion of upcoming or completed local activities.
- **Audiovisual material:** Create relevant material from the organisation of local events.
- **e-mail – Newsletters:** Assist PLANO2 with the development and update of the STEP mailing lists by providing contact information of local stakeholders.
- **Informational material:** Translate content and develop the relevant material (brochures, conference material, etc.) using the available templates and content in English language
- **Presentations:** Participation in third-party events for the dissemination of the project’s context.

Monitoring & evaluation – Phase 4:

These activities will take place throughout the duration of the project, gaining special feedback from the completion of the previous dissemination phases, as well as from the rest of the project activities. For this, partners should report on regular basis (every 3 months) on the related activities undertaken.

Activities	Monitoring	Deadline
Feedback and dissemination activities	• Report on feedback and dissemination activities	Every 3 months (starting from March 2016)

5 Monitoring, Reporting & Evaluation

To ensure accurate monitoring and reporting of dissemination activities, STEP deliverables include a number of reports linked to dissemination activities. All STEP partners should report on dissemination activities to PLANO2 every 3 months or less, and PLANO2 is responsible for compiling the content of these reports, under the guidance of DRAXIS.

The reporting schedule for the formal STEP dissemination deliverables is as follows:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (in months)
D7.6	2 nd Network of Interest	Report	Public	23
D7.5	2 nd Report on dissemination activities	Report	Public	24
D7.8	3 rd Report on dissemination activities	Report	Public	30
D7.9	3 rd Network of Interest	Report	Public	30

This involves two main types of reports:

- Annual Reports on the Network of Interest
- Annual Reports on dissemination activities

As mentioned above, PLANO2 is in charge of the overall monitoring of all dissemination activities and reports to the project coordinator in case of any problem, and of monitoring the achievement of the dissemination KPIs set in the proposal phase. However, each partner is in charge of locally monitoring its own dissemination activity and reporting the progress and pitfalls to PLANO2. All partners are responsible for liaising with national and local media for dissemination purposes, and for ensuring that they engage enough stakeholders to properly enlarge the STEP community.

In order to qualify and evaluate the dissemination actions, STEP has set specific measurable goals. The implementation of the dissemination strategy will be regularly evaluated according to the level of realisation of set up dissemination objectives and results.

6 Dissemination timeplan

The dissemination activities and the relevant action plan that will be executed within the second year of the STEP project are presented in the following Table.

Activity	Delivery Date
Deliverables	
D7.6 - 2 nd Network of Interest	April 2017
D7.5 – 2 nd Report on dissemination activities	May 2017
D7.8 – 3 rd Report on dissemination activities	November 2017
D7.9 – 3 rd Network of Interest	November 2017
Social media	
Creation of STEP social media accounts for all the pilot areas	September 2016
Promotional material	
Online STEP tutorial	November 2016
2 nd project leaflet	June 2016
2 nd STEP newsletter	June 2016
3 rd STEP newsletter	November 2016
4th STEP newsletter	May 2017
5th STEP newsletter	November 2017
3 rd press release	November 2016

D7.7: 2nd Dissemination Plan

4 th press release	May 2017
5 th press release	November 2017
Project events	
Launch events in the pilot areas	December 2016 – January 2017
Project workshop no. 1	May 2017
Project workshop no. 2	October 2017
Project conference	November 2017
Webinar no. 1	November 2016
Webinar no. 2	May 2017

7 Conclusions

During the first year of the project implementation, significant progress has been made on the dissemination of the project and its objectives so that a wide audience was informed. Some of the dissemination measurable targets set at the STEP proposal phase have been reached to a great extent, while for some other metrics the consortium should put extra effort until the end of the project to achieve the targets. In this aspect, the present deliverable describes the minimum dissemination activities that should be executed from M13 until M30.

ANNEX I – Reporting Templates

This annex includes the reporting templates for: a) dissemination publications, and b) dissemination events. All partners are required to send information on all dissemination publications and events to the WP7 leader using these templates.

Template for Reporting Dissemination Publications

Date	DD/MM/YY
Task	Which dissemination activity does this publication belong to?
Description	Type of publication/ published where/ title of article
Estimated Reach	Number of people the activity has reached
Target Audience	Describe the type of audience this activity has reached
Partners involved	Partner acronym
Results	Did you receive any response? Was the story picked up somewhere else?
Link	If the publication/article is online, please provide a link

Template for Reporting Dissemination Events

Event title, place, dates	Seminar/ infoday/ bilateral meeting/ fair trade/ stand City, Country DD/MM/YY
Event aim & purpose	Write 2-4 lines to describe the objectives of the event and link to the project objectives
Impact to the project	Write 2-4 lines about the impact of such an activity to the project, e.g. create awareness about the project's outcomes, encourage involvement, create synergies with organisations or projects, collaboration agreements with third existing parties, strengthen links with public bodies, consolidate exploitation position, etc.
Type of audience	Write the type of audience that attended the event
Target audience reached	Write the type of audience that you reached during the event
Size of audience	Write the number of all people that attended the event
Coverage Level	Local/ regional/ national/ European level

Partners involved	Partner acronym
-------------------	-----------------

Brief report and feedback gathered

- Write 1-2 lines to describe the content and the goal of your presentation/presence
e.g. Content: present project introduction
e.g. Goal: increase public visibility, stakeholders attraction and involvement, etc.
- Write 2 or more lines for any comment you received from the audience that you consider useful and explain how the consortium should utilise this
- Write 1-2 lines about a follow-up / post-meeting you have arranged with any stakeholder

ANNEX II – Report on the formation of the local core teams

This template will be used for the reporting on the relevant activities that have been undertaken by each pilot partner for the formation of the local core teams. Specifically, as set out in the local dissemination strategy, the core teams should:

- consist of at least 5 persons
- include members from the project team/personnel of the partner, as well as local experts from relevant disciplines
- be responsible for the overall coordination of the local dissemination activities.

Each of the pilot partners is requested to fill in the relevant information accordingly in the following table.

Please indicate the persons comprising the core team		
Name	Position, Organisation	Expertise
Please indicate the means used to contact and engage the members		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • personal communication (e.g. phone, e-mail, etc.) • open/ targeted call for relevant experts; • other (please specify) 		
Please indicate any relevant issues/ problems experienced in the recruitment of the core team members		
Please indicate any other relevant activities undertaken, which have not been covered above		